

Vol.34 No.1 2021

Print ISSN: 0971-8184
Online ISSN: 0976-1926

Indian Journal of Plant Genetic Resources

*An International Journal for
Conservation and Use of Plant Diversity*

Indian Society of Plant Genetic Resources
New Delhi, India

cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* L. var. *botrytis* L.) germplasm for resistance to downy mildew [*Hyaloperonospora parasitica* Constant (Pers.: Fr) Fr.] and designing appropriate multiple

resistance breeding strategies. *J. Hort. Sci. Biotechnol.* **88**(1): 103-109.

47. AHW/BR-5 (IC0627526) (IC0627526; INGR19079), a Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) Germplasm with Stable Andromonoecious Sex Form

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Watermelon [*Citrullus lanatus* (Thunb.) Matsam. & Nakai] is an important crop belonging to Cucurbitaceae family with ($2n=2x=22$). Watermelon act as a coolant, thirst-quencher, detoxifier, diuretic, febrifuge, and, according to some natural healers, an aphrodisiac. The fruits of watermelon are fleshy, juicy and sweet. Mostly eaten fresh, provide a delicious and refreshing dessert in hot weather. The major nutritional components of the fruit are carbohydrates (6.4 g/ 100g), vitamin A (590 IU) and lycopene (4100 µg/ 100g), an anti-carcinogenic compound found in red flesh of watermelon which is beneficial in prevention of heart attacks and certain types of cancer. It is a rich in iron content among all members of cucurbitaceous crops. The rind is rich in citrulline, an amino acid that contributes to the removal of ammonia from the body and wound healing. Watermelon is native to Tropical Africa chiefly the Kalahari Desert (the current nations of Namibia and Botswana) where wild forms are still found (De Candolle, 1882). Whitaker and Davis (1962) also describe the existence of a secondary

diversification centre in India. Watermelon is thought to have been domesticated in Africa at least 4000 years ago and now grown worldwide, particularly in regions with long, hot summers (Robertson, 2004).

A wide range of genetic variability has been observed in quantitative and qualitative traits of watermelon (Choudhary *et al.*, 2016). Watermelon is mainly monoecious (staminate and pistillate flowers borne on the same plant separately) in sex expression however, andromonoecious (staminate and perfect flowers borne on the same plant) sex form is also found rarely. Identified an andromonoecious plant from segregating population and homogenized through repeated inbreeding. The developed material (AHW/BR-5; IC-0627526) possess unique trait *i.e.* stable andromonoecious sex form and able to set fruits under net house conditions without pollinators and produced viable seeds. AHW/BR-5 produced round, red fleshed fruits having light green rind devoid of stripes in 80-85 days after sowing weighing 2.08-2.78 kg with 10.80-11.74% TSS and 1.38-1.92 cm thick rind.

Table 1. Salient characteristics of AHW/BR-5 (IC-0627526)

Trait	Description
Days taken to produce 50% pistillate flowers after sowing	45-50
Node number at which first female flower appeared	9-12
Days to first fruit harvest after sowing	80-85
Fruit weight (kg)	2.08-2.78
Fruit diameter (cm)	14.68-17.80
Rind thickness (cm)	1.38-1.92
TSS (%)	10.80-11.74
Sex form	Andromonoecious
Leaf shape	Pentalobate
Fruit shape	Round
Rind colour	Light green devoid of stripes
Flesh colour	Red

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